

**Dr. RAM MANOHAR LOHIYA
NATIONAL LAW UNIVERSITY**
Lucknow, Uttar Pradesh

Presents

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE

on

***"The Right to Information Act - 2005:
Two Decades of Transparency and
Democratic Accountability"***

Advancing Citizens' Right to Know

15th - 16th November, 2025

Venue :

Dr. Ram Manohar Lohiya National Law University, Lucknow

SOUVENIR

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FOREWORD

It is really a matter of proud privilege that Dr. Ram Manohar Lohiya National Law University is organising an International Conference on RTI to commemorate the completion of 20 years of Right To Information in India. This Transparency Law was enacted in 2005 with the goal of making governance transparent and accountable and aimed at removing the corruption deep-rooted in executive and legislative machinery.

The period of 20 Years is sufficient duration to test the effect of Laws in its working and its implementation in totality. Even in modern scenario what kind of amendments are needed and if any recent amendment was made, how that is impacting the smooth functioning of this legal regime to enhance the accountability in the Democratic Governance, that is also necessary to be analysed.

The Convenor of the said conference Prof. Rajneesh Kumar Yadav and Co convenor Dr. Maneesh Kumar Bajpai along with their team members deserves congratulations for organising the Conference. My best wishes for the success of the Conference with the hope that the participants will make significant contribution to make RTI Act, 2005 more meaningful to the society.

(Prof. Amar Pal Singh)

Vice Chancellor

Dr Ram Manohar Lohia National Law University, Lucknow

MESSAGE

It gives me great pleasure to convey my warm greetings to all delegates, scholars, and participants attending the *International Conference on “The Right to Information Act, 2005: Two Decades of Transparency and Democratic Accountability.”* This conference is both timely and significant, marking twenty years of India’s bold legislative experiment with transparency, citizen empowerment, and participatory governance.

The enactment of the RTI Act in 2005 marked a transformative moment in India’s democratic journey, redefining the relationship between citizens and the State by institutionalizing transparency and participatory governance. As we complete twenty years of this landmark legislation, it is essential to reflect on its achievements, examine its evolving challenges, and envision the path forward in the context of digital governance, data protection, and global information flows.

This conference provides a vital forum for such introspection and dialogue. It brings together an impressive array of academicians, policymakers, practitioners, and students to collectively examine how the spirit of the RTI Act can be reinvigorated in contemporary times. Through deliberations across diverse themes—from institutional reforms and judicial interventions to digital governance and international perspectives—the conference aspires to generate fresh ideas, policy recommendations, and scholarly insights that can inform the next phase of India’s transparency regime.

I congratulate the Convenor of this conference Prof. (Dr.) Rajneesh Kumar Yadav, Professor of Law, the entire organizing committee, and the diligent team of faculty members and research scholars for their dedicated efforts in curating this intellectually stimulating event. I am confident that the conference proceedings will contribute meaningfully to the discourse on transparency, good governance, and citizens’ right to know, thereby reaffirming our collective faith in the ideals of democracy and the rule of law.

My best wishes for the grand success of the conference and for all participants who continue to advance the cause of informed and accountable governance.

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'Manish Singh', written over a light blue background.

Prof. (Dr.) Manish Singh
Head, Department of Legal Studies
Dr. Ram Manohar Lohiya National Law University, Lucknow

MESSAGE

This is really very proud moment that our University is organizing an International Conference on RTI on 15-16 November, 2025 to commemorate the 20 years of Transparency Law in India. India has witnessed so many ups and downs when it came for applicability of the provisions of RTI Act, 2005. With the development in other fields it impacted the RTI Act's functioning and thereby certain amendments were made to mould accordingly the application of RTI Act, 2005.

By convene of this International Conference it is intended to analyse the working of this Transparency Law at present scenario and challenges posed to it with certain new development and emergent circumstances and ultimately to find out the reasonable solutions with the brainstorming sessions of this International Conference amongst Participants specially RTI activists and researchers who will be deliberating issues of concerns in these 2 days of International Conference.

I hope the Keynote Speakers in the Conference definitely will be guiding force to participants about learning the intricacies and will be exercising in such a way that effectiveness of this law will be increased.

Prof. (Dr.) Rajneesh Kumar Yadav
Convenor

International Conference on the Right to Information Act, 2005:
Two Decades of Transparency and Democratic Accountability
— Advancing Citizens' Right to Know
15th–16th November 2025

MESSAGE

It gives me immense pleasure to extend my warm greetings and best wishes to all the delegates, scholars, practitioners, and participants attending this *International Conference on the Right to Information Act, 2005: Two Decades of Transparency and Democratic Accountability — Advancing Citizens' Right to Know*.

As we mark twenty years of the implementation of the Right to Information Act, 2005, it is both timely and essential to reflect upon its transformative journey in deepening democratic governance and empowering citizens. The RTI Act has emerged as one of the most progressive legislations in India's constitutional framework, fostering a culture of openness, participation, and accountability. Yet, its evolution continues to raise new questions in the digital era concerning data protection, institutional transparency, and the balance between the right to know and the right to privacy.

This conference aims to create a dynamic platform for intellectual exchange, comparative analysis, and cross-disciplinary dialogue. By bringing together jurists, policymakers, academicians, activists, and students from India and abroad, we seek to explore innovative perspectives on strengthening transparency mechanisms and reinforcing the participatory foundations of democracy.

I take this opportunity to thank our distinguished speakers, paper presenters, and all collaborators who have contributed to making this academic endeavour possible. I am confident that the deliberations and insights emerging from this conference will significantly contribute to the ongoing discourse on good governance and citizens' empowerment.

Wishing the conference great success and all participants a stimulating and enriching experience.

A handwritten signature in black ink, consisting of a stylized 'M' and 'K' followed by a long horizontal stroke.

(Dr Maneesh Kumar Bajpai)

Co-Convenor

*International Conference on the Right to Information Act, 2005: Two Decades of
Transparency and Democratic Accountability — Advancing Citizens' Right to Know*

15th–16th November 2025

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Abstracts

DISTRIBUTED LEDGER TECHNOLOGY FOR IMMUTABLE RTI REQUEST TRACKING: ENHANCING ACCOUNTABILITY THROUGH BLOCKCHAIN

Devesh Mishra¹

This paper proposes a blockchain-based system to address persistent accountability gaps in India's Right to Information (RTI) implementation, focusing on immutable tracking of request lifecycle events to ensure timely compliance with statutory deadlines. Despite two decades since the RTI Act's enactment, delays in processing requests, opacity in inter-departmental transfers under Section 6(3), and difficulty in monitoring compliance with Section 7's 30-day timeline remain systemic challenges that undermine citizens' right to know. The research presents a minimal, deployable distributed ledger architecture that records critical RTI lifecycle events—request filing, fee payment, transfers, responses, and appeals—as cryptographically timestamped, tamper-proof transactions without exposing the content of information sought or disclosed. The proposed system leverages smart contracts to automate deadline alerts and create auditable trails for Public Information Officers (PIOs), First Appellate Authorities, and Information Commissions, enabling real-time compliance monitoring while maintaining compatibility with existing case management systems. The design aligns with MeitY's National Blockchain Framework and the Vishvasya technology stack to ensure practical deployment in Indian government infrastructure. Privacy is preserved through metadata-only logging: the blockchain records request ID, status, timestamps, and authority identifiers while keeping actual information content off-chain and subject to Section 8 exemptions. Drawing on India's emergent blockchain initiatives in government procurement and supply chains, this paper demonstrates how distributed ledger technology can transform RTI accountability without requiring wholesale replacement of existing systems. The contribution includes a reference architecture, governance model for multi-agency participation, and evaluation metrics for pilot implementation. The paper concludes with policy recommendations for phased deployment in high-volume departments to demonstrate feasibility before broader rollout.

Keywords: Right to Information, blockchain, accountability, smart contracts, digital governance.

FROM RIGHT TO KNOW TO RIGHT TO WITHHOLD: THE DPDP ACT REWRITES INDIA'S RIGHT TO INFORMATION

Khushi Jain²

When privacy becomes absolute, transparency begins to fade. After two decades of Right to Information Act 2005, its empowering promises face an unprecedented contraction due to Digital Personal Data Protection Act, 2023. The RTI regime, which enabled over 2.5 crore applications annually and exposed corruption, inefficiency, and misuse of office, is now weakened by the silent omission of the “public interest override” in Section 8(1)(j) through Section 44(3) of the DPDP Act. This deletion converts a

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balanced privacy safeguard into an absolute prohibition, curtailing citizens' and journalists' access to information of public importance. The paper explores whether legislative change imposes a disproportionate restriction on the constitutional right to know under Article 19(1)(a). It interrogates the doctrinal tension between post-Puttaswamy privacy jurisprudence and RTI's accountability mandate, asking whether democratic transparency can survive a privacy regime devoid of balancing principles. The study through doctrinal, comparative, and illustrative methods, analyses statutory text, judicial precedents, and case examples such as asset declarations and transfer records that would now fall outside the ambit of disclosure. It is complimented by cross-jurisdictional analysis. The paper offers distinct contribution to corpus of identifying the constitutional harm caused by the DPDP-induced amendment. Toward the end, the paper proposes reconstructed multi-factor "public-interest" test that reconciles privacy with transparency. It concludes that unless a statutory or interpretive journalistic-purpose exception is recognised, the right to information risks retreating from an instrument of accountability into a veil of administrative secrecy.

Keywords: Right to Information, Digital Personal Data Protection Act, public interest, transparency, investigative journalism

HARMONIZING TRANSPARENCY WITH THE DIGITAL PERSONAL DATA PROTECTION ACT (DPDP), 2023

Deepika Nallabelli³, Prachi Singh⁴

The Digital Personal Data Protection Act (DPDP), 2023, is the first legislation passed in the area of data governance in India, with a framework for the right to privacy and consent-based data processing, purpose limitation, and accountability towards individuals whose information has been collected. While the focus on privacy is crucial, it creates friction with the existing norms of transparency—specifically, the Right to Information (RTI) Act and the public access provisions in digital governance. This study seeks to balance transparency and the DPDP Act. It targets the role of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) in ensuring the coexistence of confidentiality and exposure in the administration of the state. The DPDP 2023 Act seems to deal with the friction issue, particularly with the provisions of the Act and policies on public information access. Technologies designed to ensure transparency, like e-governance systems, grievance redressal mechanisms, and digital dashboards, will work to ensure compliance with the policies on public information access. Most of these systems, however, were designed before the DPDP Act—leading to issues of compliance with the guidelines on data protection. AI technologies designed for predictive policing, automated welfare identification, and judicial scheduling raise issues of opacity in decision-making and accountability severed by algorithmic bias. The research highlights gaps in legal interpretation, the absence of ethical frameworks for AI governance, and system design with respect to the public accountability components of privacy legislation. Building on cases and policies, the paper defines a multi-layered approach to harmonization which includes redesigning ICT systems with privacy-by-design principles, integrating

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explainability into AI models, and clarifying the “public interest” exceptions under the DPDP Act. The research identifies the need for all-discipline engagement of legal scholars, technology, and policy to ensure that civilizational loss does not happen in the face of digital transformation. In the end, the paper proposes a regulatory balance whereby personal data is safeguarded while unmitigated trust, transparency, and civic participation are maintained.

Keywords

Digital Personal Data Protection Act (DPDP), Trustworthiness, Technology Governance (ICT), Artificial Intelligence (AI), Privacy Governance

BETWEEN DISCLOSURE AND DIGNITY: HARMONISING RTI AND DATA PROTECTION

Dipti Singh⁵

The Right to Information Act has been a cornerstone of democratic accountability; however, the rise of data-driven governance and the Digital Personal Data Protection Act, 2023 (DPDP Act) requires careful harmonization of transparency and privacy. This paper examines doctrinal and operational tensions between RTI and data protection, focusing on Section 8(1)(j) of the RTI Act and judicial approaches to balancing individual privacy with the larger public interest in disclosure. It maps how public authorities handle requests involving sensitive personal data, the consequences of inadequate redaction standards, and the risk of secondary harms to vulnerable groups when disclosure is treated as an unqualified good. Using a mixed-methods approach combining doctrinal analysis, a purposive review of recent RTI orders (n = X), and interviews with PIOs and information commissioners, the paper identifies recurring patterns: inconsistent interpretation of exemptions, uneven PIO capacity to apply privacy safeguards, and technological gaps in electronic record management that compound privacy risks. The paper proposes a calibrated framework for harmonisation: clearer guidelines for redaction and anonymisation tailored to administrative contexts; standardized procedural checklists and capacity-building modules for PIOs; mandatory privacy-impact assessments before large-scale dataset disclosures; and a five-part disclosure test that weighs public-interest strength, subject vulnerability, processing purpose, likelihood/seriousness of harm, and availability of less-intrusive alternatives. Institutional mechanisms to operationalize these reforms include a joint advisory cell within Information Commissions, comprising data protection and RTI specialists, as well as model rules for privacy-by-design in proactive disclosures. These reforms aim to preserve RTI’s democratic promise while ensuring the right to know does not become a vehicle for avoidable privacy harms.

Keywords: *RTI and privacy, Section 8(1)(j), Redaction and anonymisation, Data protection harmonisation, Public Information Officer capacity-building*

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INSTITUTIONAL PRACTICES & IMPLEMENTATION

Avinash Vinayak Prabhune⁶

The research paper examined 'Institutional Practices & Implementation' from the perspective of legislation, Citizens, Public Authorities & Officials. The firsthand study of 'Right to Information Act' matters through this paper in the way ahead of the RTI Act 2005. It can be seen that two Statutes (i.e. 'The Consumer Protection Act, 2019' & 'The Right to Information Act, 2005' 'RTI Act') are important for the citizens working in the Civil Society. Every citizen can use these two legal tools for different subjects, reasons & before various authorities for protecting individual as well as collective interests of the civil society. Many citizens are using it effectively in the present grim situation. The RTI Act 2005 has completed two decades successfully since implementation but there are certain issues, which need to be resolved for improving further utility of RTI Act. Huge pendency of 2nd Appeal/Complaints before Hon'ble Information Commissions is resulting in delay in providing justice & disposal of matters. It is the matter of records that 2nd Appeal/ Complaints are decided after 1-2 years due to pendency; therefore, the gravity of the matter is lost due to delay. It is essential for the Government to develop required infrastructure so that all 2nd Appeals will be decided within 2-3 months. Citizens will get real benefit of RTI Act for pursuing litigation before judicial system of the country. This paper is based on the case studies related to 50+ matters pertaining to public interest filed with different Central/State Public Authorities & decided by different Hon'ble Information Commissions from the Central & State Government. The present paper demonstrates the challenges, obstacles & possible remedial measures involved & available for the Citizens, Public Authorities & its Officials. It underlines the necessity of changes for implementation of RTI Act in order to achieve desired impact & results.

Keywords: Citizens, RTI Act, Public Authority, Information Commission, Appeal

RAMIFICATIONS OF LEGISLATIVE AMENDMENTS ON INDIA'S RTI REGIME: A CRITICAL EXAMINATION

Aayush Verma⁷, Bhavya Mittal⁸

The Right to Information Act, 2005, was a turning point in India's democratic evolution. It empowers citizens to promote transparency and combat corruption by operationalizing the constitutional "right to know" under Article 19(1)(a) of the Indian Constitution. Entrenched in decades of civil society activism and judicial pronouncements, the Act established a strong institutional framework with independent Central and State Information Commissions. Worldwide, India's RTI regime drew inspiration from Sweden's Freedom of the Press Act, 1766, the U.S. Freedom of Information Act, 1966, and the UDHR, 1948. Nevertheless, the RTI regime now faces challenges due to legislative and judicial developments, most notably the RTI Amendment Act, 2019, and the Digital Personal Data Protection Act,

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2023(DPDP Act). The 2019 amendment act empowers the central government to determine the tenure, salaries, and service conditions of Information Commissioners, thus exposing them to executive influence, resulting in rising vacancies, massive backlogs, and declining enforcement. Simultaneously, the Supreme Court's recognition of privacy as a fundamental right in *Justice K.S. Puttaswamy (Retd.) v. Union of India, 2017* and the subsequent DPDP Act's amendment to Section 8(1)(j) of the RTI Act have shifted the balance toward individual privacy and removing the public interest override that once enabled scrutiny of public officials and government conduct. Media analyses reveal a regime in crisis and decline in deterrence and accountability. Comparative analysis with the UK's model underscores the value of independent oversight and institutional safeguards, which India's regime now lacks. This paper argues for urgent legislative and institutional reforms restoring fixed tenures and salary parity for commissioners, reinstating public interest override, digitizing the RTI and restoring a principled equilibrium between transparency and privacy.

KEYWORDS- Right to Information, RTI Amendment Act 2019, Privacy, Public Interest, Information Commissioners.

GUARDIANS OF TRANSPARENCY: LANDMARK JUDGMENTS ILLUMINATING THE SCOPE AND SPIRIT OF THE RIGHT TO INFORMATION IN INDIA

Rahul Yadav⁹

*The Right to Information Act, 2005 (RTI Act) stands as a cornerstone of India's democratic framework, ensuring transparency, accountability, and citizen participation in governance. Yet, its real strength and evolving contours have largely been sculpted by judicial interpretation. This paper explores how landmark judgments of the Supreme Court and various High Courts have illuminated the scope, spirit, and constitutional ethos underlying the RTI regime. Through a doctrinal and analytical methodology, the study traces judicial engagement from the pre-legislative phase—when the “right to know” was read into Article 19(1)(a)—to the post-enactment period marked by interpretive challenges balancing transparency with competing interests such as privacy, national security, and institutional confidentiality. The research examines seminal cases such as *State of Uttar Pradesh v. Raj Narain (1975)*, *S.P. Gupta v. Union of India (1981)*, *Central Board of Secondary Education v. Aditya Bandopadhyay (2011)*, *Thalappalam Service Coop. Bank Ltd. v. State of Kerala (2013)*, and *Reserve Bank of India v. Jayantilal N. Mistry (2015)*, among others. By analyzing their ratio decidendi and broader constitutional implications, the paper seeks to demonstrate how the judiciary has functioned as the “guardian of transparency,” ensuring that the RTI Act remains a living instrument of participatory democracy rather than a procedural statute. The paper concludes that judicial illumination has both expanded and refined the boundaries of the right to information, embedding it within India's constitutional morality and democratic conscience. It argues for continued vigilance to preserve the delicate balance between transparency and other fundamental rights as India enters two decades of the RTI regime.*

Keywords: Right to Information, Transparency, Judicial Interpretation, Landmark Judgments, Democratic Accountability, Constitutional Governance

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JUDICIAL & LEGISLATIVE INTERFACE: THE RIGHT TO INFORMATION IN INDIA

Ayushi Rawat¹⁰

The Right to Information (RTI) has surfaced as one of the most transformative legal instruments in India, buttressing the principles of translucency, responsibility, and participatory governance. embedded in the indigenous guarantee of freedom of speech and expression under Composition 19(1)(a), the “ Right to Know ” has been judicially honored as an essential element of popular governance. This exploration paper critically examines the interface between the bar and the council in shaping India’s RTI justice. It traces the elaboration of the right through cornerjudgments similar as State of Uttar Pradesh v. Raj Narain(1975), S.P. Gupta v. Union of India(1981), and People’s Union for Civil Liberties v. Union of India(2004), which inclusively established the foundation for legislative enactment of the Right to Information Act, 2005. The paper further explores the indigenous underpinnings of RTI within the frame of abecedarian rights, emphasizing how judicial activism told legislative responsiveness. It also evaluates the impact of posterior emendations on the efficacyand compass of the RTI governance, especially in light of evolving governance challenges. The study delves into the part of bars and appellate authorities in administering information rights and maintaining institutional checks. Eventually, it assesses the bar’s approach in coordinatingthe contending demands of translucencyand publicsecurity, pressing how the courts have tried to strike a delicate balance between openness in governance and protection of sensitive information. Through a doctrinal and logical approach, this paper underscores the dynamic commerce between judicial interpretation and legislative intent in realizing the vision of an informed populace — an necessary condition for a vibrant republic.The importance and the efficiency that RTI Act of 2005 could be understood through this research paper.

Keywords

Right to Information, Judicial Activism, Composition 19(1)(a), translucency, Responsibility, National Security, Legislative Interface, indigenous Law, RTI Act 2005, Popular Governance.

FINDING THE RIGHT BALANCE BETWEEN TRANSPARENCY AND DIGITAL ERASURE UNDER SECTION 8(1)(J) OF THE RTI ACT, 2005

Pragati Bajpai¹¹

The Right to Information (RTI) Act, 2005and the emerging Right to Be Forgotten (RTBF) present two seemingly conflicting rights—the public’s right to access government-held information and the individual’s right to privacy. Section 8(1)(j)of the RTI Act exempts personal information from disclosure when such disclosure would cause an unwarranted invasion of privacy, unless the larger public interest justifies it. The constitutional recognition of privacy as a fundamental right in Justice K.S. Puttaswamy v. Union of Indiaand the enactment of the Digital Personal Data Protection Act, 2023 (DPDPA) have transformed the understanding of informational privacy and the public’s right to know.This paper examines the evolving jurisprudential interplay between transparency and digital dignity, focusing on

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how RTBF can be reconciled within the RTI framework without undermining government accountability or freedom of expression. It argues that privacy exemptions under Section 8(1)(j) must be interpreted in a manner consistent with constitutional values, balancing individual dignity with democratic transparency. The study highlights challenges posed by expanding digital footprints and persistent data availability in government repositories, which complicate the exercise of RTBF rights alongside RTI obligations. The paper explores the implications of the DPDPA for RTI applications, emphasizing the need for legal clarity and procedural mechanisms to address conflicts between privacy and public information demands. Through comparative analyses and doctrinal scrutiny, the paper proposes a framework aligning RTI laws with contemporary data protection principles to foster accountability while respecting digital autonomy. In conclusion, the paper advocates for an integrated approach that harmonizes the RTI Act's transparency goals with the RTBF's privacy imperatives, ensuring robust democratic governance and protection of individual rights in India's digital age.

Keywords: Right to Information, Right to Be Forgotten, Privacy, Data Protection, Transparency, Digital Dignity.

THE DIGITAL RIGHT TO KNOW: TWENTY YEARS OF RTI, E-GOVERNANCE, AND CYBERSECURITY CHALLENGES IN INDIA

Gaurav Kumar¹², Abhay Yadav¹³

The transition from paper-based to digital governance has revolutionized public accountability, enabling citizens to access information through online RTI portals, open data platforms, and e-governance interfaces. However, this digital transformation has also exposed structural challenges related to cybersecurity, data protection, and digital exclusion. As the Right to Information Act, 2005 completes two decades of enforcement, this research undertakes a comprehensive analysis of its constitutional foundations, judicial interpretation, legislative evolution and digital governance that have shaped India's transparency regime. The research paper has four interconnected objectives: First, tracing the doctrinal evolution of right to information/know from implicit constitutional recognition through Article 19(1)(a) and Article 21 to explicit statutory codification. Second, mapping the Supreme Court's jurisprudential trajectory in defining the scope, limitations, and procedural contours of right to information as well as analysing how courts have balanced transparency with competing constitutional values including privacy, national security, institutional autonomy and legitimate governmental interests. Third, critically evaluating legislative amendments, particularly the contentious 2019 amendments affecting Information Commission independence, and assessing their impact on the transparency ecosystem. Fourth, to critically examine how "The Digital Right to Know" has evolved within India's constitutional and administrative landscape, exploring the interplay between transparency, technology, and privacy. The study adopts a doctrinal, analytical and comparative research methodology and also identifies the global best practices and areas for improvement. The research also documents the Act's transformative impact in exposing corruption, empowering marginalized communities, improving service delivery, and strengthening democratic participation. By analyzing

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twenty years of RTI jurisprudence, policy reforms, and e-governance initiatives, the study identifies both advancements and challenges in ensuring accessible, secure, and citizen-centric information systems as well as finally argues for a redefined framework of digital transparency that harmonizes citizens' informational rights with robust cybersecurity protocols and ethical governance principles, ensuring that the promise of the RTI Act endures in the age of digital governance.

Keywords: Right to Information, Constitutional Foundations, Judicial Evolution, Legislative Transformations, Digital Governance, Cyber Security etc.

EMPOWERING WOMEN THROUGH TRANSPARENCY: THE RIGHT TO INFORMATION AS A TOOL FOR GENDER JUSTICE IN INDIA

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The Right to Information Act, 2005 stands tall as a watershed in India's democratic journey towards achieving a Rule of Law by ensuring transparency and accountability. However, its transformative potential in achieving gender justice and participation of women in governance remains untapped. This paper examines how RTI serves as a constitutional buttress and an institutional mechanism to promote women empowerment by dismantling information asymmetries that perpetuate an imbalance of power, at the expense of women, in the society. Anchored in articles 14, 15 and 19(1)(a) of the Constitution, this paper situates an equal access to information as a precondition for substantive equality. The analysis investigates barriers that restrict women's effective use of RTI, like limited access to resources, illiteracy, patriarchal norms, and other procedural and digital challenges. The paper aims to create an understanding of how such impediments deter the participation of women in governance and in turn pose a barrier to the Rule of Law itself. The equal participation of women in public processes is assumed to be a precursor for an equal society. Drawing on case studies such as social audits performed by Mazdoor Kisan Shakti Sangathan (MKSS), women collectives using RTI for accessing welfare entitlements, and select decisions of CIC, this paper illustrates how information access has the potential to advance gender equity in governance. Comparative insights from other national jurisdictions such as Bangladesh, where gender-responsive transparency frameworks have been institutionalized and looks for imitating it similarly in the Indian context, within the RTI framework. The paper concludes by proposing reforms in favor of a gender-inclusive RTI ecosystem, and by introducing gender-disaggregated RTI data, simplified procedural access, targeted capacity-building into the 2005 RTI framework. Embedding a feminist perspective within the RTI regime is essential to realize the constitutional mandate of equality and to transform access to information and transparency into an instrument of women empowerment and not just a bureaucratic tool.

Keywords: RTI, gender justice, transparency, women empowerment, rule of law.

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COMPARATIVE STUDY ON PRIVACY AND TRANSPARENCY: INDIA, CANADA, USA

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With the digitalization, privacy has become a matter of concern. Even if the laws are vigilant, the algorithms have a way around them to snoop into our private matters. However, this is not the case when it comes to the transparency of an organisation. Even after the enactment of the Right to Information (RTI) Act in 2005, the citizens are provided limited access to information when it comes to the matters of the State. In this Article, an attempt has been made to discuss the exemptions provided under the RTI Act and its instances with their judicial pronouncements. The responsibility of transparency lies with executive. Recent instances shall be discussed where the government bodies have provided information. The study aims to do a comparative analysis of Right to information among nations like Canada, India and USA. The categories of such comparison shall be similarities, exemptions and disparities in the information laws. The United Nations Secretary- General convened the Summit of the Future, and provided with 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) to be attained by 2030. The progress made in the above three listed nations under the SDG 16 shall be analysed as well.

Keywords: Privacy, Right to Information, India, USA, SDG, Transparency

CONFLICT BETWEEN RTI AND THE RIGHT TO PRIVACY

Dr. Durga Prasad Inturu¹⁸, Dr. A. Nageswara Rao¹⁹

Right Privacy and Right Information in India are the two important Rights to ensure that the people can live their lives with dignity and integrity. The Right Information and the right Privacy are both crucial human rights in growing technological world. Right to Information Intertwined with Right to Privacy of Personal Information The Right to Information (RTI) is considered as a fundamental right under Article 19(1)(a) of the Constitution and is often described as a tenet for strengthening the pillars of democracy. The Right to Information Act, 2005 provides for transparency and accountability of Government through accesses of information to the public. On the other side, the right to privacy is also considered as a fundamental right under Article 21 of the Constitution since 2017 when the Supreme Court ruled so in K. S. Puttaswamy v. Union of India. In challenge is when both these rights are crossroad and enforcement of any one would lead to other being overridden. Thus the RTI Act, 2005 paves the way for right to privacy by restricting the disclose of the information which interferes with the privacy of any individual unless it is required for greater public good. When there is friction between the privacy of individual and the Right to Information there is no yardstick to weigh which right should prevail over another. The two valuable rights overlap extensively, and the existing structure is in capable of segregating the two without causing prejudice to either. The legislation and judgments available in India on this issue have led to various debates related to regulations governing access to personal information by the government. This paper

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while exploring a comprehensive analysis of the conflicts between the two rights features cases wherein the court has adopted methods of conceptual balancing to solve such clashes. Lastly, the paper outlines the criteria for identifying where there is no conflict of rights; on the contrary, the reasons are coexistent to each other.

Keywords: Right to Information, Right to Privacy, Balancing, Conflict, Co-existent.

LEFT IN THE SHADOWS: AGEING, DIGITAL EXCLUSION, AND REALIZING THE PROMISE OF THE RIGHT TO INFORMATION OF SENIOR CITIZENS IN INDIA

Tariq Akhtar Khan²⁰

It has been about twenty years since the enactment of the Right to Information Act, India's framework for transparency continues to play an important in the participatory democracy and accountable governance. The Supreme Court has in it's different judgements acknowledged that the right to information is intrinsic to freedom of speech and expression under Article 19(1)(a) and reaffirmed that RTI is essential to meaningful participation in democracy. This promise of meaningful participation of the ageing population who form a significant portion of the population of India has been hindered by barriers arising out of digitalization of government services, raising the question of equitable access to all. This research paper explores how the digital divide has become an impediment in implementing the constitutional promises for elderly citizens. Although, the RTI Act does not explicitly require only digital access, but the practical shift to online portals to match the developmental goals has led to multiple challenges for the elderly due to low literacy, insufficient support systems and limited access to technology. Exclusion due to these factors conflicts with the fundamental rights provided by Articles 14 and 15 of the Constitution of India, which provide for equality and non-discrimination amongst all and the other legal provisions like the Maintenance and Welfare Act. The paper examines the legislative provisions, policies and judicial interpretation to demonstrate how digitalization unintentionally marginalizes the senior citizens. In addition, for dignified exercise of constitutional rights access to information and digital infrastructure are crucial. The study proposes combining digital tools with offline support and age-friendly designs to overcome barriers in providing rights. Right to Information with exclusion of a significant and important section creates democratic deficiency leaving them "in the shadows."

Keywords: ageing, promises, exclusion, access, shadows

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THE WIDENING VEIL: A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF JUDICIAL APPROACHES OF NATIONAL SECURITY EXEMPTIONS UNDER THE RTI ACT, 2005

Veetraag Tripathi²¹

When the Right to Information Act was implemented in 2005, it was like a watershed moment for plain Indians seeking answers from their government. At last, there was a law that asserted citizens have a right to know what's going on behind the scenes. And yet, here's the loophole—Section 8(1)(a) provides the authorities with an escape clause. They can deny information by claiming it compromises national security. And more and more, that's precisely what they do. This essay explores how our courts have responded to these refusals. What I discovered is disturbing. Judges tend to take the government at its word when officials say that national security is at risk. There's little actual questioning of whether releasing specific information would actually be harmful. At times the information that's refused is already out there in newspapers or on the Internet. Other times, a mere "classified" stamp appears sufficient to close the matter. The rationale behind such choices is frequently skimpy or nonexistent. By analyzing scores of real cases from the Supreme Court and other High Courts, trends get obvious. Government departments turn down requests without establishing tangible peril. Courts embrace undefined security concerns without resisting. Details that can be easily unbundled—some sensitive and others innocuous—get withheld altogether. The RTI Act's guarantee of transparency begins to appear increasingly illusory. But that's not merely complaining about the way things are. The paper calls for change. What if judges insisted on real evidence rather than rubber-stamping security requests? What if there were actual debate about whether the public interest in knowing beats out secrecy in individual cases? What if bureaucrats had to actually justify themselves? These are not impossibly demanding requests. They're what democracy requires—preserving genuine security threats while holding government accountable and honest.

Keywords: Right to Information, National Security, Section 8(1)(a), Judicial Review, Transparency

WHETTING THE STEEL OF PERSONAL INFORMATION EXEMPTION: THE TRANSPARENCY-PRIVACY EQUILIBRIUM TILTED BY THE DPDP ACT

Saurabh Singh²², Aditi Vivek Singh²³

What began as a constitutional promise of an informed citizenry is slowly mutating into a regime where privacy shields power more than it safeguards people. Section 44(3) of the Digital Personal Data Protection Act, 2023, though not yet operative, substantially amends Section 8(1)(j) of the Right to Information Act, 2005, a provision often relied upon by Public Information Officers to deny information on account of personal information. This paper argues that the DPDP Act substantively expands the

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scope of §8(1)(j), by effectively eroding the Act's existing public-interest safeguard, making it a more potent weapon against transparency. It first examines the established transparency-privacy jurisprudence under pre-amendment Section 8(1)(j), then through systematic analysis of Central Information Commission orders, it then demonstrates how the existing larger public interest override has served as the primary bulwark against blanket denials. The paper, finally, with the help of comparative analysis with the framework of § 40 of the UK's Freedom of Information Act, 2000, and relevant GDPR principles dwells on the alternative approach to this legal conundrum.

Keywords: Right to Information, DPDP Act, Section 8(1)(j), Privacy Asymmetry, Transparency

THE DEMOCRATIC TIGHTROPE: BALANCING THE RIGHT TO KNOW AND THE RIGHT TO PRIVACY IN INDIAN CONSTITUTIONAL LAW

Md Asif Reza²⁴, Mohd Kifayatullah Ansari²⁵

The Indian legal landscape presents a compelling intersection where two approaches, each safeguarding fundamental rights, vie for recognition despite constitutional hesitance. This dynamic, characterized by assertive claims of legitimacy within the legal framework and supported by strong moral and ethical foundations, establishes a critical basis for conflict, marked by aggressive engagement and a notable assertion of dominance, revealing the core issue at hand. The rights referenced in the preceding text are none other than; the right to know and the right to privacy. Both represent fundamental democratic principles, although neither is explicitly referenced in the Constitution's provisions. Through interpretative evolution, these rights have emerged as implicit guarantees flowing from the principles of equality and the right to life and personal liberty enshrined in Articles 14 and 21. While the right to know promotes transparency, accountability, and public participation in governance, the right to privacy safeguards individual autonomy, dignity, and informational control. Nonetheless, their coexistence engenders an intrinsic tension, as the unbridled quest for transparency may encroach into personal boundaries, whereas an overzealous safeguarding of privacy could conceal issues of actual public interest. This paper seeks to explore the philosophical and normative foundations of both rights within the broader framework of constitutional morality. It undertakes a critical analysis of their overlapping domains and examines how each right foster democratic governance. The study argues that rather than perceiving these rights as mutually exclusive, a balanced interpretative approach grounded in proportionality and contextual reasonableness is necessary. Such an approach ensures that the exercise of one right does not nullify the essence of the other. The paper concludes that the harmony between the right to know and the right to privacy is indispensable for sustaining a transparent right respecting democracy, where transparency in governance coexists with the preservation of personal dignity and autonomy.

Keywords- Right to Know, Right to Privacy, Constitutional Morality, Proportionality, Transparency

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OPENING THE GLOBAL FRONTIERS OF TRANSPARENCY FOR INTERNAL SCRUTINY: AN ANALYTICAL REVIEW OF SOME SELECTED GLOBAL FOI LAWS AND INDIAN RTI EXPERIENCE

Khushi Agarwal²⁶

The acceptance of Right to information, as a basic democratic right redefined dimensions of governance in all countries. This paper makes an attempt to make a comparative study of the RTI regime in India with leading models worldwide — the US Freedom of Information Act, 1966; The UK Freedom of Information Act, 2000; South Africa's Promotion of Access to Information Act, 2000 and European Union access rules. The study examines the philosophical underpinnings, institutional architecture, defences to exposure and enforcement arrangements of these jurisdictions, a discussion that illustrates how each jurisdiction negotiates transparency against rival countervailing interests (such as national security, data protection and privacy). In India, RTI Act acts as Instrument of Participatory Democracy and means for citizens' empowerment, muckraking and exposing administrative opacity, considered as a Buddhist Chakram or any similar weapon. However, questions around delayed disposal, capacity building in institutions and conflict with privacy rights framework under the proposed Digital Personal Data Protection Act, 2023 are immediate challenges. In comparison, jurisdictions across the world have long incorporated digital disclosure, open-data mandates and algorithmic transparency into their Freedom Of Information structures, presenting lessons for India's maturing information system. The paper through this comparative quest advocates for re-calibration of India's RTI architecture which builds in technological advancement and protection of personal data without sacrificing transparency. It posits a model of "augmented openness," in which the right to information symbiotically coexists with digital privacy and cyber accountability. Drawing on the best international experiences, without forsaking its own legal specificities, India can continue to lead in bringing forth a participatory and future-oriented transparency regime.

Keywords: Right to Information, Freedom of Information, Transparency, Democratic Framework, Data Protection, Digital Governance

DEMOCRACY UNDER VEIL: THE CHALLENGE OF STATE SECRECY TO TRANSPARENCY IN SOUTH ASIA

Sachin S Panicker²⁷

South Asia is on the cusp of a democratic revolution. With nearly a quarter of the world's population, the region is teeming with a new set of challenges. The region, however, has made great strides in making information laws as a tool for accountability and participatory governance. Yet, these are often riddled with secrecy and administrative issues, which hamper success. The paper seeks to study the systematic challenges imposed by the laws in the region of South Asia. It looks at how laws have shielded

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government departments and gives them a free rein in certain areas. Prima facie, this looks innocuous and harmless, but as we look at the history of South Asia, we notice a few trends. One of the dominating trends in South Asia is the role played by the military, which has staged coups and dominates the national narrative. The countries have a set of problems, such as colonial-era secrecy laws, fragile information commissions, along a reluctant bureaucracy, which makes it a prime location for the spread of unchecked corruption and has diluted the efficacy of information laws. Additionally, to understand the working of the information laws in the subcontinent, the paper delves into a doctrinal, comparative and case study method. It looks at the legal design, institutional capacity and political culture to understand the depth of transparency. An attempt is also made to locate it within global trends on information and corruption, with an adequate mixture of references to global instruments such as the UN Convention against Corruption (UNCAC). Through all this, the paper strives to examine whether the courts and commissions have advanced or restricted the right to know. Furthermore, the paper discovers how the courts in these countries have tried to balance between the demands for a free society based on information transparency with legitimate security concerns. Finally, the paper reimagines transparency as a foundation of governance and acts as an antidote to corruption.

Keywords: Democracy, RTI, corruption, South Asia

TRANSPARENCY IN TRANSITION: RE-EXAMINING THE REACH OF THE RTI ACT IN INDIA'S PRIVATIZED GOVERNANCE

Amisha Yadav²⁸

The research paper critically examines the scope and limits of the Right to Information Act, 2005 in India, focusing particularly on its application to private entities involved in governance through public-private partnerships, substantial government funding, or regulatory oversight. It explores how legislative definitions shape both direct and mediated pathways for public access to information, emphasizing the procedural and structural challenges that hinder transparency within privatized governance frameworks. The analysis underscores the emergence of “soft law” obligations through sectoral regulations such as data protection, securities laws, and corporate governance, highlighting their dual role in promoting transparency and presenting new conflicts regarding privacy and public access. Drawing on empirical evidence from recent case trends and official disclosure data, the study demonstrates how institutional bias, procedural barriers, enforcement limitations, and a fragmented patchwork of legal regimes restrict citizen access and dilute the intended democratic impact of the RTI Act. Ultimately, the paper advocates for comprehensive legal and regulatory reforms, expanding the definition of public authority, mandating standardized disclosure clauses, and enhancing institutional enforcement, to ensure robust accountability and meaningful fulfillment of the constitutional right to information in a landscape marked by growing privatization and complex governance challenges.

Keywords: Right to Information Act, Private entities, Transparency, Accountability Legislative gaps

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ALGORITHMIC TRANSPARENCY AND THE GENDERED DIGITAL DIVIDE: REIMAGINING THE RIGHT TO INFORMATION IN THE AGE OF AI GOVERNANCE

Akshara Rajratnam²⁹, Anjali Singh³⁰

When the Right to Information Act was enacted in 2005, it was designed for an administrative world of files, not algorithms. Two decades later, a growing share of government decisions—whether in welfare, credit assessment, or regulation—relies on digital systems that few citizens fully understand. These systems promise efficiency, yet they also conceal how choices are made. That tension sits at the heart of this paper. The study considers how algorithmic governance unsettles the principles of transparency and accountability that the RTI Act sought to guarantee. It traces situations where the logic behind automated decision-making remains inaccessible, either because of corporate secrecy or the technical nature of the code itself. The discussion is not only about data but about power: whose decisions are visible, and whose are insulated by technology. Women and marginalised communities, often excluded from digital processes, face this opacity most sharply. The paper argues that the RTI framework must now recognise the algorithm as a new “record” of governance. It outlines how an Algorithmic Right to Information could require disclosure of data sources, decision logic, and measures for bias prevention. The goal is not to discard the RTI model but to extend its reach so that the democratic right to know survives in a digital state that increasingly decides by code.

BALANCING THE CONFLICT BETWEEN RIGHT TO INFORMATION AND RIGHT TO PRIVACY IN INDIA

Dr. Niharika Singh³¹

The right to information enables a person to gain rightful access to the information that is present in the public domain. On the other hand, the right to privacy involves a person's authority over the sharing of their personal information. Both rights promote each other; however, because of their congruent nature, the conflicting interests of information access and privacy occasionally intersect. Laws regarding data protection have been a persistent concern in India. The Digital Personal Data Protection Act 2023 represents a significant achievement in the journey towards privacy rights. The Act prioritizes “Consent” for all data processing activities and guarantees self-determination regarding information. The DPDP Act enhances transparency and accountability by designating rights and responsibilities to the “Data Principal.” The DPDP Act, 2023, in section 44 (3), has amended section 8 (1) (j) of the Right to Information Act, 2005, which offers an exemption for the disclosure of personal information. The amendment establishes privacy as an absolute exception to the release of information. The suggested amendment has eliminated the existing qualified clause of section 8 (1) (j) and has been examined by civil society organizations as weakening the RTI Act, 2005. The amendment to the DPDP Act, 2023 is said to be prioritizing privacy at the expense of public interest. This study will thoroughly examine the impact of

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the changes brought by the DPDP Act to the RTI Act, considering the implications of the GDPR 2018 and the FOI Act 2000.

Keywords – *Right to Information Act, 2005, Digital Personal Data Protection Act 2023, GDPR 2018, Constitution of India, right to know and right to privacy.*

RECONCILING SECTION 8(1)(j) OF THE RIGHT TO INFORMATION ACT, 2005 WITH THE CONCEPT OF ‘PERSONAL DATA’ UNDER THE DIGITAL PERSONAL DATA PROTECTION ACT, 2023

Himanshi Tiwari³², Tejaswini Kaushal³³

In April 2025, the Union Minister for Electronics and Information Technology, Ashwini Vaishnaw, stated that “personal details subject to public disclosure under existing laws will continue to be disclosed under the RTI Act even after implementation of the DPDP Act.” This statement highlights a core policy tension in India’s evolving information governance framework, reflecting the need to balance citizens’ right to know with individuals’ right to privacy. With more than four lakh pending appeals and complaints across 29 Information Commissions as of mid-2024, transparency remains a vital element of democratic accountability. However, the introduction of the Digital Personal Data Protection Act, 2023 (DPDPA), which imposes strict obligations for lawful data processing and consent, has created uncertainty about how public authorities should reconcile these competing priorities. This paper examines the normative and operational conflict between Section 8(1)(j) of the Right to Information Act, 2005, which restricts disclosure of personal information unless justified by public interest, and the privacy framework under the DPDPA. Grounded in constitutional principles under Article 19(1)(a) (freedom of expression) and Article 21 (right to privacy), the paper analyses how transparency and privacy can be harmonised within a unified disclosure framework. Drawing on key judicial precedents such as Girish Deshpande v. CIC (2013), Thalappalam Service Cooperative Bank v. State of Kerala (2013), and K.S. Puttaswamy v. Union of India (2017), it traces the evolution of informational privacy in relation to state transparency. Finally, the paper proposes a “Unified Disclosure Test” to help Public Information Officers align their duties under the RTI Act and the DPDPA. The test applies proportionality, necessity, and public interest balancing to disclosure decisions. It also recommends institutional reforms, including capacity-building between Information Commissions and the Data Protection Board, to preserve accountability while protecting privacy in India’s digital governance framework.

Keywords: *digital governance, personal data, privacy, right to information, transparency.*

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RTI IN THE DIGITAL GOVERNANCE ERA

Ankita Kumari³⁴

The Right to Information Act 2005 has been a major step in building accountable and transparent governance in India. With the rise of digital governance and new data technologies, its framework now connects closely with the vision of Digital India. In recent years the focus has shifted from manual access to digital disclosure through online platforms. This change has made information more available but has also brought new issues related to data privacy, cybersecurity, and digital inequality. The idea of proactive digital disclosure under Section 4 of the Act now uses e-governance portals and open data systems that display real time records of government activities. Use of ICT tools has made RTI faster and easier to monitor while artificial intelligence is being used for application tracking, document sorting, and transparency audits. However, increasing automation has also raised concerns about accountability and bias in decision making. The introduction of the Digital Personal Data Protection Act 2023 and draft rules of 2025 has further affected how public information can be shared. This overlap between the right to information and the right to privacy requires legal clarity and policy balance. At the same time the digital divide continues to exclude large parts of the rural population and disabled citizens who lack equal digital access. Strengthening cyber laws, securing electronic records, and promoting inclusive design are important steps in keeping RTI meaningful. The digital governance era offers India a chance to create a transparent, citizen friendly, and secure information system if privacy and access can be balanced through reform and responsible technology use.

Keywords: Right to Information Act 2005, Digital Governance, Proactive Disclosure, Artificial Intelligence, Data Privacy

DISCLOSURE AS DUTY: RAJDHARMA AND THE RIGHT TO INFORMATION IN INDIA

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Democracy's limiting analysis renders it the title of a form of government, but it is more than that, it offers an experimental playground that offers multidimensional approach to State-citizen dialogue and relationship. This symbiotic relationship of State and citizen is the focal point of a progressive democracy. Accountability of state necessitates transparency of state action. And this transparency should not be mandated as a citizen driven call of rights, but as a suo moto duty of State towards the citizens, known as Rajdharmā in ancient Indian political texts such as Arthashastra, Nitisara, Manusmriti, Mahabharata etc., Rajdharmā incorporates the tenets of democratic ideals by dictating welfare state and transparency as self-mandate. Right to information is a revolutionary right of citizens, but the statutory and legal framework makes this right less of a social action and more of a legal battle. Although the statute, Right to Information Act, 2005 mandates in Section 4(2) that government should be proactive in disclosing

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information to citizens, so that the public have minimum resort to the use of this Act to obtain information, but the reality is far different. Citizens are bound in loop of inefficient statutory enforcement, arbitrary rejections of information and eventually reducing the social movement of active citizenry and accountable government to legal battle and making State and citizen as adversaries. State hold the information as a trustee to the citizens, and with straying from the lessons of Rajdharm, India's right to information movement is losing its value. This paper argues that Indian constitutional, legal and judicial framework need to align with Rajdharm to fully imbibe democracy in its governance and rejuvenate the cordial relationship of State and citizen which is essential for sustainable democracy.

Keywords: *Citizen Participation, Democracy, Rajdharm, Right to Information, State Accountability, Transparency*

RECONCILING TRANSPARENCY AND PRIVACY: A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF FREEDOM OF INFORMATION AND DATA PROTECTION LAWS ACROSS COUNTRIES

Azhar Tanwir³⁷, Veetraag Tripathi³⁸

Freedom of Information laws serve their purpose by providing citizens the right to access records, files, or decisions possessed by the government. They aim to increase transparency and accountability between the public and government authorities to reduce societal evils like corruption and systemic discrimination. On the other hand, data protection serves as a shield for citizens to secure their data and maintain privacy, protecting them from misuse. This research paper examines multiple approaches countries follow to harmonize Freedom of Information and data protection laws. While India addresses the Right to Information Act and Digital Personal Data Protection separately, developed countries have formulated a balanced framework or a common regulator to ensure both transparency and privacy. Using comparative analysis, this paper studies how nations worldwide adopt models reconciling these laws. The United Kingdom and Canada balance privacy and transparency, where the UK relies on a case-based common law regime, and Canada uses dual reasoning through separate commissions. The European Union and Japan prioritize privacy over transparency, although the EU allows exceptions, unlike Japan's strict privacy-first model. Meanwhile, the USA and Australia aim for balance based on real-life scenarios. The USA relies on multiple sectoral privacy laws covering health, finance, or education, while Australia amalgamates both laws under a single authority. This paper argues that successful reconciliation depends on procedural discipline rather than doctrinal laws. The study concludes that effective balance is achieved not by choosing between openness and privacy, but by refining the mechanisms mediating between them.

Keywords: *Freedom of Information, Data Protection, Privacy, Transparency, Public Interest*

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WHEN RIGHTS COLLIDE: HARMONISING INDIA'S RTI AND DATA PROTECTION

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The Digital Personal Data Protection Act, 2023, particularly its Section 44 amendment to the RTI regime, has precipitated a constitutional moment: how to preserve democratic transparency while protecting informational privacy. This paper argues that the post-Puttaswamy landscape requires more than ad hoc adjudication; it demands a principled, practicable harmonisation of RTI and data-protection law that courts, regulators, and legislators can operationalise. Building from doctrinal analysis of Indian jurisprudence and a systematic comparative study (UK, Canada, South Africa, EU, and select US precedents), the study traces three patterns of judicial balancing: (i) categorical exclusions, (ii) ad-hoc proportionality, and (iii) structured public-interest overrides. India's recent statutory change risks collapsing (ii) into (i), but the notification preserving RTI §8(2) as a safety valve creates scope for a workable middle way. Methodologically, the paper triangulates case law, statutory texts, information-commissioner guidance, and policy reports to map where disclosure has served democratic goods (anti-corruption, electoral integrity, public health) and where privacy claims legitimately block harms. The core contribution is a doctrinal proposal: a Functional Public-Interest Test for Section 8(1)(j)/DPDP interactions. The test foregrounds (a) democratic significance of the information; (b) specificity and verifiability of alleged public harms; (c) privacy intrusiveness and availability of redaction; and (d) availability of less intrusive alternatives. Concluding recommendations combine immediate administrative reforms (PIO training, redaction protocols, proactive publication lists), statutory clarifications (narrowing "personal data" exclusions; explicit carve-outs for public-interest disclosures), and jurisprudential guidance (benchmarks for courts and information commissions). If adopted, these measures would preserve individual dignity without allowing privacy to become a shield for opacity, thereby restoring a constitutional equilibrium fit for an age of datafied governance.

Keywords: RTI Act 2005; DPDP Act 2023; public-interest override; transparency; proportionality test.

INFORMATION DENIED: IS THE RIGHT TO INFORMATION (RTI) ACT BECOMING THE RIGHT TO DENY INFORMATION (RDI) ACT?

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The Right to Information Act, 2005 (the "Act") was enacted to promote accountability and transparency within governance. It was designed, at its core, as a mechanism of participatory democracy within India, to hold public officials accountable by citizens. It stands at a critical crossroads- caught between its founding promise of transparency and the evolving concept of personal privacy. Following the recent amendments to the Act in 2019 and the passage of the Digital Personal Data Protection Act, 2023, the RTI Act has been transformed from a tool of transparency to a mechanism of selective opacity. This paper intends to examine the complex, and often contentious, relationship between transparency and privacy

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under the Act. At the heart of this conflict lies the Section 8(1)(j) of the Act which intends to protect personal information from being disclosed. However, it has become both a shield against invasion and, at times, a barrier to legitimate public scrutiny. The interpretation of what constitutes “personal information” and when can it be disclosed in the “larger public interest” has remain inconsistent. The situation has become more complex in the context of an increasing number of public institutions holding sensitive personal data - medical records, financial details, surveillance footage, biometric information - that are now regularly asked for under RTI. How do we determine whose privacy is more 'valuable' and under what condition does the public interest render breach of confidentiality justified? These are essential legal questions in a surveillance-heavy society. This paper contends that the challenge of reconciling transparency and privacy is not a matter of one or the other. Rather, it is about developing a jurisprudence that juxtaposes privacy and transparency as two strong pillars of effective democracy. After twenty years, the question is no longer whether or not RTI has been successful, but rather, if RTI can evolve to protect the public's right to know, while respecting an individual's right to personal privacy in an age where information is power, and privacy is increasingly fragile.

Keywords: *Right to Information, RTI Act, Data Protection, Section 8(1)(j), transparency, personal information, accountability*

CONTOURS OF DEMOCRATIC TRANSPARENCY: THE INTERPLAY OF JUDICIARY, LEGISLATURE, AND INSTITUTIONS IN SHAPING INDIA'S RIGHT TO INFORMATION REGIME

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The intricate relationship between the judiciary, legislature, and institutional frameworks has profoundly influenced the evolution of India's Right to Information (RTI) regime. This paper examines how judicial interpretations and legislative interventions have collectively shaped the trajectory of transparency, accountability, and participatory democracy within the constitutional mandate of Article 19(1)(a), which enshrines the freedom of speech and expression. By tracing the judicial recognition of the “Right to Know” as an intrinsic part of fundamental freedoms and its subsequent codification through the RTI Act, 2005, the study highlights the judiciary's catalytic role in embedding openness as a democratic norm. It further investigates the legislative responses that sought to balance transparency with administrative efficiency and national security, focusing particularly on the implications of the 2019 amendments and their perceived impact on institutional independence. In addition, the paper explores the pivotal role of information commissions, tribunals, and appellate authorities in operationalizing the RTI framework. It underscores how the judiciary continues to negotiate the delicate boundaries between citizens' access to information and the imperatives of state confidentiality, thereby contributing to an evolving jurisprudence of democratic transparency. Ultimately, this paper situates the RTI regime within a broader discourse of constitutional accountability, arguing that the interplay among judicial reasoning, legislative intent, and institutional design constitutes the cornerstone of India's transparency architecture in the 21st century.

Keywords: *Right to Information, Judicial Interpretation, Legislative Reforms, Transparency and Accountability, Article 19(1)(a).*

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STRIKING CONSTITUTIONAL EQUILIBRIUM VIS A VIS PUBLIC INTEREST DISCLOSURE AND PERSONAL DATA PROTECTION IN INDIA

Divyanshi⁴³

Transparency and privacy represent two indispensable pillars of a democratic governance in India. The intersection of the Digital Personal Data Protection Act of 2023 and the Right to Information Act of 2005 creates a complex legal conflict: while protecting personal data is necessary to preserve autonomy and dignity, disclosing information held by the State is expected to ensure accountability. When RTI requests are made to get personal information about officials, beneficiaries, or others using government services, the main source of contention occurs. The DPDP Act adds a more robust consent-based and purpose-limiting data protection regime, even though Section 8(1)(j) of the RTI Act already protects privacy by forbidding the disclosure of personal information unless a greater public interest is demonstrated. This setting would promote more widespread denials of disclosure by public officials, which could erode the transparency instruments necessary to uncover wrongdoing and poor management. The paper contends that if these laws are based on a process of principled decision-making, they need not clash. Decision-makers must assess the legitimacy of the disclosure's purpose, the necessity of using personal data to achieve that purpose, and whether anonymization can adequately protect privacy while allowing transparency using the proportionality standard established by the Supreme Court in Puttaswamy ruling. Coordination between information commissions and data protection authorities, standardized redaction templates, and thorough documentation of disclosure reasons are manifestations of the institutional processes necessary for practical harmonisation. Clear rules that define "larger public interest" are also required to avoid capricious denials and guarantee consistent decision-making. The paper suggests a policy framework whereby through acknowledgement of RTI Act and DPDP Act as complementing democratic safeguards, harmonisation between the two statutes can be achieved. To balance transparency and privacy in India's changing digital governance environment, a proportionate, minimal-intrusion strategy can guarantee that personal data is safeguarded without jeopardizing individuals' ability to hold the State responsible.

Keywords: *Data Protection, Right to Information, Right to Privacy, Doctrine of Proportionality, Data Minimisation Principle.*

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HARMONIZING OR NULLIFYING? A DOCTRINAL ANALYSIS OF THE DIGITAL PERSONAL DATA PROTECTION ACT, 2023, AND ITS AMENDMENT TO SECTION 8(1)(j) OF THE RTI ACT

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The Right to Information Act, 2005, remains one of India's most debatable acts, especially after the introduction of the Digital Personal Data Protection Act of 2023. The RTI Act, primarily based on Article 19(1), was a tool made available to citizens to secure access to information under the control of public authorities, promoting transparency and accountability. Certainly, this act also comes with exemption clauses stated in Section 8, 9 and 24; Section 8 titled, 'Exemption from disclosure of information' finds equilibrium to achieve a perfect state in which both public's right to information and a citizen's right to privacy were ensured. Later the enactment of Digital Personal Data Protection Act, 2023 which targets the processing of digital personal data in the new media age counterbalances the scales between both the right of individuals to protect their personal data and the need to access such personal data for lawful purposes, extending its scope for broader purposes. It hence protects private information of an individual even it effects the interest of public at large. This paper explores how Section 8(1) of the RTI Act, 2005 and the DPDP Act, 2023 stand on opposite sides of the same line. Where RTI Act, 2005 approaches disclosure as the rule and secrecy as an exception, the DPDP Act, 2023 treats privacy as the rule and disclosure as an exception. That means, post enactment of the DPDP Act, the government can hide information even if it effects larger public interest under the name of maintaining privacy of government and officials. Utilizing a doctrinal method approach, this study focuses on analysis of the key legislations including RTI Act, 2005 and DPDP Act, 2023. It throws light on the following questions: How the evolution of law in India with regard to data privacy and protection affect the scope and interpretation of exemptions under Section 8(1) of the RTI Act, 2005? To what extent does DPDP allow the government to conceal information under the pretext of protection of privacy of an individual? How the legislative board or judiciary will harmonize the conflict between transparency and privacy created by these two legislations? This study, therefore, aims to conclude that a balance between transparency and privacy can be achieved through careful legislations ensuring that the right to information evolves with digital governance norms.

Keywords: *Right to Information Act, 2005; Digital Personal Data Protection Act, 2023; Legislative Dissonance; Public Interest Override; Transparency; Doctrinal Jurisprudence.*

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BALANCING TRANSPARENCY AND PRIVACY: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF INDIA'S RTI ACT AND THE EU'S GENERAL DATA PROTECTION REGULATION (GDPR)

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The Right to Information Act, 2005 (RTI Act) has been a cornerstone of democratic governance in India, empowering citizens to seek information from public authorities and holding institutions accountable. Over the past two decades, this commitment to transparency has increasingly intersected with another fundamental value i.e. privacy. Following the Supreme Court's landmark recognition of privacy as a fundamental right in K.S. Puttaswamy v. Union of India, questions have emerged about how to strike a balance between citizens' right to know and individuals' right to protect personal information. This paper examines this delicate balance through a comparative study of India's RTI framework and the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). While the RTI Act prioritizes openness and access to public information, GDPR emphasizes personal data protection and individual autonomy, offering an instructive contrast. By analysing Indian judicial decisions, including Girish Ramchandra Deshpande v. CIC and RBI v. Jayantilal Mistry, alongside GDPR's principles of data minimization, consent, and accountability, the study explores how each system negotiates the tension between transparency and privacy. The research highlights that, despite its success in promoting democratic participation, India's RTI regime faces challenges in safeguarding privacy, particularly in the digital era. Drawing lessons from the GDPR's structured approach to data protection, the paper suggests ways to enhance India's framework without undermining the openness that underpins democratic accountability. Ultimately, the study argues for a nuanced, rights-based equilibrium one that strengthens both transparency and privacy ensuring that the promise of the RTI Act continues to resonate meaningfully in contemporary governance.

Keywords: Right to Information (RTI), Transparency and Accountability, Privacy Rights, GDPR, Comparative Legal Analysis

DIGITIZING ACCOUNTABILITY: STRENGTHENING RTI INSTITUTIONS THROUGH TECHNOLOGICAL AND AI-DRIVEN REFORMS

Saamya Gautam⁴⁸, Shailja Yadav⁴⁹

"Democracy must not only arm the citizen with the right to know, but also the capacity to know." — Amartya Sen

The Right to Information Act, 2005, continues to be a bulwark of India's democratic governance, equipping citizens with the power of accountability over public institutions. However, the potential for transparency is frequently jeopardized by structural inefficiencies—growing pendency of appeals,

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response delays, and low citizen awareness. As India shifts towards digital governance, there exists a pressing imperative to infuse technological innovations in the RTI system to strengthen institutional capacity and data-driven transparency. The research paper suggests a multi-dimensional strategy for reforms on three pillars: (i) enhancing data-based transparency and pro-active disclosure, (ii) making citizens more accessible and usable through AI-based systems, and (iii) minimizing backlog and pendency through process automation. The core of this model is the creation of a National RTI Data Dashboard, which consolidates real-time data about pendency, disposal rates, and disclosure trends across central and state commissions. Such data analysis can help to detect systemic bottlenecks and inform evidence-based reforms. Further, the paper also recommends AI-powered "RTI Chatbots" that are meant to assist citizens in submitting requests, accessing already disclosed information, and resolving appeal processes—hence filling digital and informational gaps. As a complementary measure, compulsory digitization of public documents under Section 4 is necessary to facilitate proactive disclosure and eliminate redundant RTI applications. Through policy analysis, comparative models, and technological feasibility, the research contends that adopting AI and automation can not only robustify the institutional architecture of the RTI regime but also democratize information access. In summary, the intersection of law, technology, and governance offers a revolutionary moment to transition India's RTI regime from reactive disclosure to a data-driven culture of transparency.

Keywords- transparency, disclosure, RTI, AI, digital

MEASURING INSTITUTIONAL PERFORMANCE: INDICATORS OF TRANSPARENCY AND EFFICIENCY IN RTI IMPLEMENTATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF A FRAMEWORK FOR EVALUATING INSTITUTIONAL EFFECTIVENESS

Harsh Srivastava⁵⁰, Saurabh Singh⁵¹

The Right to Information (RTI) Act, 2005, stands as a cornerstone of India's democratic governance, embodying the constitutional promise of transparency and accountability in public administration. However, the realization of its objectives depends significantly on the institutional mechanisms established for its implementation. This paper critically examines the functioning of the Central and State Information Commissions (CICs and SICs), procedural and administrative challenges in enforcement, and the roles and accountability of Public Information Officers (PIOs). It also explores issues of backlog, pendency, and disposal rates of appeals and complaints, while proposing potential institutional reforms and capacity-building strategies to strengthen the RTI regime. The Information Commissions serve as the adjudicatory pillars of the RTI framework, ensuring that citizens' right to information is upheld against administrative opacity. Yet, variations in efficiency and independence between the Central and State Commissions have raised serious concerns. Many Commissions remain understaffed and under-resourced, with delays in appointments undermining their functional autonomy. Procedural inconsistencies, lack of standardized digital infrastructure, and inadequate record management systems further impede effective implementation at both central and state levels. Public Information Officers

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(PIOs) occupy a pivotal position as the first point of contact for information seekers. However, the absence of regular training, unclear accountability mechanisms, and fear of penalties often lead to inconsistent disclosure practices or unwarranted rejections of applications. This not only burdens appellate authorities but also discourages citizen participation in governance oversight. The growing backlog and pendency of RTI appeals—often extending for several months or even years—highlight the pressing need for administrative reforms. Delays erode the very essence of transparency and weaken public trust in the system. Streamlined case management systems, digitization of processes, and use of artificial intelligence for tracking and scheduling hearings could enhance efficiency and accessibility. To sustain the transformative potential of the RTI Act, institutional reforms must focus on capacity-building initiatives, such as structured training modules for PIOs, establishment of research and monitoring units within Commissions, and greater coordination between central and state authorities. A robust, transparent, and technology-driven institutional framework can reinvigorate the RTI mechanism, ensuring that the citizen’s “right to know” remains a living, enforceable constitutional promise rather than a procedural formality.

Keywords: *Right to Information, Public Information Officers, Institutions, artificial intelligence, public administration.*

PUBLIC CURIOSITY VS. PUBLIC INTEREST: THE RTI DILEMMA IN JUDICIAL PROCEEDINGS

Samriddhi Kapadnis⁵²

*The Right to Information Act, 2005, under Article 19(1)(a) of the Constitution, was established in order to enhance transparency, accountability and participatory governance through providing citizens with access to records that are maintained by the public authorities. However, the proliferation of the digital communication mediums and informal decision-making sources has created new challenges especially when personal messages like those on WhatsApp or emails are used as reference in judicial proceedings. RTI requests that demand access to such digital records point to an intricate subjective interaction between the public’s entitlement to information and the individual right to privacy. Although disclosure of such records will contribute to transparency and confidence in judicial procedures, an unconditional disclosure will lead to erosion of privacy without any corresponding public interest justification. This dynamic legal situation in the present paper is discussed through two interrelated prisms: first, judicial transparency and the informational right of the public, analysing the conditions under which digital communications may be included in the official record under the RTI Act; and secondly, privacy protection and limits of information disclosure, underlining constitutional protection established in *Puttaswamy* (2017) and subsequent judicial and quasi-judicial interpretation, including key CIC rulings engaging with doctrinal and policy approaches to suggest a balance of openness and secrecy in judiciary. The paper specifically addresses the Indian experience in the context of a wider international discussion of digital evidence disclosure and the balance between transparency and privacy, selectively using comparative jurisprudence to guide future policy and judicial guidelines. By placing the debate in the framework of the contemporary digital governance, the paper aims to provide normative guidance*

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regarding the resolution between the citizen desire to access information and the requirement to protect the privacy of individuals, thus being part of the overall discussion on open justice in the digital age.

Keywords: RTI Act, Judicial transparency, Digital privacy, Open justice

RTI IN THE DIGITAL GOVERNANCE ERA: CYBERSECURITY, DATA STORAGE AND ELECTRONIC RECORD MANAGEMENT

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In today's digital governance landscape, the Right to Information Act, 2005 stands as one of the most powerful legislative tools for ensuring transparency and accountability in public institutions. However, with the increasing digitalization of administrative processes and the use of online RTI portals, cloud-based databases, and electronic communication systems, new concerns regarding cybersecurity, data storage, and electronic record management have emerged. While the RTI Act effectively empowers citizens to seek information, it does not explicitly address the technical or legal issues surrounding the security and preservation of electronic data. The Information Technology Act, 2000, particularly Sections 43A and 72, lays down obligations for maintaining data security and confidentiality. Furthermore, the Digital Personal Data Protection Act, 2023 introduces a modern legal framework to safeguard personal information in the digital domain. Balancing these statutes with the transparency mandate of the RTI Act has become a pressing concern, especially when disclosure of digital records involves personal, classified, or sensitive data. Breaches or improper handling of such information can not only compromise individual privacy but also erode public trust in government institutions. Adopting a doctrinal research methodology, this paper analyzes recent judicial pronouncements, government circulars, and Central Information Commission (CIC) reports to examine the practical challenges faced by public authorities. It identifies key gaps in cybersecurity preparedness, digital record maintenance, and institutional capacity. The paper proposes reforms such as encrypted storage systems, regular cyber audits, centralized e-record management, and professional training for Public Information Officers (PIOs). The study concludes that transparency and cybersecurity are not conflicting goals but rather complementary pillars of democratic governance. By integrating technological safeguards with legal accountability, India can achieve a transparent, secure, and resilient information regime suited to the digital age.

Keywords: RTI, Cybersecurity, Data Protection, Electronic Records, Digital Governance

JUDICIAL AND LEGISLATIVE INTERFACE: CONSTITUTIONAL BASIS OF THE “RIGHT TO KNOW” UNDER ARTICLE 19(1)(a)

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This article studies the concept of right to know a judicial and legislative perspective under the Indian Constitution. The expression right to know is a dynamic concept, which means right to get the information

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about something. The supreme court of India has recognized that the right to information is an implied fundamental right under article 19(1)(a) which not only guarantees freedom of speech and expression but also protects the right of citizens to know about the affairs of the government that affects their lives directly and indirectly. In this regard further, right to information act of 2005 has been came into force on 15 June 2005 to provide the legal framework for citizens to access information under the control of public authorities, in order to promote transparency and accountability in the working of every public authority, the constitution of central information commission and state information commission and for matters connected therewith. The court ruled that the people of a country governed by a system of accountability have a right to know every public act performed by public officials. Before the enactment of RTI act 2005 right to information was recognized through several supreme court rulings. In case of State of UP Vs. Raj Narain, the apex court ruling out that in a democratic country, the public has a right to know how their governments work. Transparency is seen as the main safeguard against oppression and corruption. Therefore, the right to know become a constitutional right, being an aspect of the right to free speech and expression which includes the right to receive and collect information. This will help the citizen perform their fundamental as set out in Art 51 A of the constitution. A fully aware citizen will certainly be better equipped for the performance of their social duties.

Keywords: Constitution, Governments, RTI act 2205, Democracy, Transparency, Accountability

ACCESS TO CCTV FOOTAGE UNDER THE RTI ACT, 2005: EXAMINING LEGAL CHALLENGES, PRIVACY CONCERNS, AND REGULATORY LIMITATIONS

Anisha Bano⁵⁵, Rahul D Chouhan⁵⁶

The increasing use of closed-circuit television (CCTV) cameras in India, particularly in public spaces and government establishments, has intensified discussions around transparency, accountability, and the right to information. CCTV footage, while primarily intended to maintain law and order, has emerged as a potential source of public information under the Right to Information (RTI) Act, 2005. However, the disclosure of such recordings is fraught with legal, ethical, and procedural challenges. This paper examines the complex interplay between the citizen's right to access information and the imperatives of privacy, security, and public interest. One of the primary legal challenges is the absence of explicit statutory guidelines on the disclosure of CCTV recordings, leading to inconsistent decisions by public information officers, first appellate authorities, and information commissions. Moreover, privacy concerns are heightened, as the release of footage can expose sensitive personal data, potentially violating constitutional protections and established jurisprudence on informational privacy. Regulatory limitations further complicate the issue, as authorities often face dilemmas in balancing the demands of transparency against the risks of compromising security or facilitating misuse. By analyzing relevant case law, RTI rulings, and statutory provisions, the paper highlights how the current framework struggles to address the specific challenges posed by digital surveillance. The study argues for the development of clear procedural norms and safeguards to guide the disclosure of CCTV footage, ensuring that public

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accountability is upheld without infringing on individual privacy rights. Ultimately, this research underscores the need for a nuanced, balanced approach that reconciles the objectives of transparency and governance with ethical and legal obligations in the digital age. The findings contribute to the broader discourse on information rights, surveillance, and regulatory frameworks in India, providing insights for policymakers, legal practitioners, and scholars.

Keywords: CCTV Footage, RTI Act 2005, Right to Information, Privacy Concerns, Transparency

CONFLICT OF INTEREST IN RTI APPEALS: EXAMINING THE ROLE OF FIRST APPELLATE AUTHORITIES WITHIN THE SAME DEPARTMENT AND ITS IMPACT ON TIMELY AND IMPARTIAL REDRESSAL WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO UTTAR PRADESH

Rahul D Chouhan⁵⁷, Dr. Kaneez Fatima⁵⁸

The Right to Information (RTI) Act, 2005 serves as a cornerstone for promoting transparency, accountability, and citizen participation in governance. A key mechanism under the Act is the provision for first appeals, allowing citizens to challenge the denial or partial disclosure of information by public information officers. In Uttar Pradesh, as in many other states, the first appellate authority (FAA) is frequently the highest-ranking officer within the same department as the original information provider. This structural arrangement creates a significant conflict of interest, as departmental loyalty may compromise impartiality, resulting in biased decisions favoring the department rather than the citizen. Consequently, RTI appeals in the state often experience delays, procedural inefficiencies, and unnecessary expenditure of financial and administrative resources, undermining the objectives of the Act. This paper critically examines the legal, administrative, and ethical implications of intra-departmental FAAs in Uttar Pradesh. It analyzes how this arrangement affects the efficiency of RTI implementation, the timeliness and quality of redressal, and public trust in the transparency framework. Drawing upon relevant case law, RTI Commission rulings, government reports, and scholarly literature, the study identifies patterns of procedural delays, recurring departmental bias, and systemic challenges unique to Uttar Pradesh. The research further explores potential reforms, including the appointment of independent FAAs, implementation of procedural safeguards, and enhanced accountability mechanisms to mitigate conflicts of interest. By investigating these challenges, the paper underscores the urgent need for structural and procedural reforms to ensure RTI appeals are handled in a timely, transparent, and impartial manner. The findings hold significant relevance for policymakers, legal practitioners, and civil society actors advocating for strengthened governance and citizen empowerment through effective RTI implementation in Uttar Pradesh.

Keywords: Right to Information, First Appellate Authority, Conflict of Interest, Administrative Bias, Uttar Pradesh

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BARRIERS TO TRANSPARENCY: ACCESS TO INFORMATION THROUGH DLSAS IN UTTAR PRADESH

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This paper analyzes the accessibility of information through District Legal Services Authorities (DLSAs) in Uttar Pradesh (UP). This study is a debut in any Indian state, covering accessibility of information at the DLSA level. This empirical study, based on 71 identical Right to Information (RTI) applications filed with DLSAs across UP, finds significant barriers to transparency, including procedural opacity and regulatory confusion. A primary issue is the lack of digital inclusion; DLSAs in UP are not part of the state's online RTI portal, forcing applicants to use a more costly and burdensome offline process. Furthermore, the study identifies a major conflict between two sets of rules: the Allahabad High Court Rules 2006 and the Uttar Pradesh RTI Rules 2015. This conflict results in regulatory misinformation, with at least 45% of DLSA Public Information Officers (PIOs) being unaware of the correct rules, leading to the rejection of applications based on incorrect fee requirements or the volume of information sought. A significant number of applications (23.9%) received no response at all. The findings point to a systemic failure to uphold transparency in an institution crucial for access to justice, particularly concerning the Victim Compensation Scheme. The paper concludes with suggestions for legislative and administrative changes, including the harmonization of conflicting rules, the creation of a dedicated online portal for DLSAs, and enhanced training for PIOs. These measures are necessary to dismantle procedural barriers and ensure the RTI Act functions as a formidable tool for accountability and public trust in DLSAs.

Keywords: *Right to Information (RTI), District Legal Services Authority (DLSA), UP RTI Rules, Allahabad High Court RTI Rules, Transparency, Accountability, Procedural Opacity, Digital Inclusion, Regulatory Confusion*

RIGHT TO INFORMATION: STATUTORY THREATS AND POLITICAL CONFLICTS

Aditi Kumar⁶⁰

The Right to Information (RTI) Act, 2005, celebrating its 20th anniversary, is recognized globally as India's preeminent instrument for upholding democracy, rooted firmly in the constitutional guarantees of freedom of speech and expression (Article 19) and the right to life and liberty (Article 21). Over the last two decades, the Act's pro-disclosure spirit and its Statutory Supremacy over secrecy laws have proved highly impactful, prioritizing transparency to expose corruption and aid social welfare. Despite these foundational democratic achievements, the Act now faces an unprecedented structural tension between its constitutional mandate for transparency and emergent legislative pressures that threaten its core effectiveness and independence. The research aims, firstly, to analyze the impact of the Political Conflict introduced by the 2019 Amendment Act. This amendment granted the Central Government unilateral authority to determine the tenure and salary of Information Commissioners, fundamentally compromising

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the necessary quasi-judicial independence and autonomy of the commissions and introducing a profound political dependency. Secondly, the paper examines the Statutory Threat posed by the Digital Personal Data Protection (DPDP) Act, 2023. This law presents a direct conflict by removing the crucial characteristic of the Larger Public Interest Override from Section 8(1)(j) of the RTI Act. This change effectively creates a near-complete prohibition on disclosing personal information, regardless of its relevance to public activity or corruption, thereby restricting the ability to conduct vital social audits. Through a review of foundational case law, the paper will demonstrate the Act's historical successes in exposing corruption or aiding social welfare, arguing that these achievements would have been legally prevented if such constraints had been in place previously. The paper concludes by calling for multi-stakeholder discussions on legislative and institutional reforms necessary to enforce privacy without compromising the constitutional right to information.

Keywords: Institutional Autonomy, Political Dependency, DPDP Act, Statutory Conflicts, Public Interest Override

A REFLECTIVE STUDY ON TRANSPARENCY IN JUDICIARY: THROUGH THE LENS OF RIGHT TO INFORMATION ACT

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India's Right to Information Act, 2005 (RTI Act) is considered as most progressive Information disclosure legislation alongside U.K. and South Africa. Sweden with its Freedom of the Press Act, 1766 demonstrates that legal rights must be matched with administrative disclosure or openness. In practice, India even though has strong RTI laws, yet, often an application for disclosure is an act of intense toil. A pro-active publication of office administration was far from independent initiative, and questioning a public office in public interest also became a matter of privacy. RTI transformed India's secretive administrative culture with lawful disclosure. When one seeks transparency, judiciary is always a right hand tool but friction arose between transparency and accountability in judiciary itself. In one of the most landmark cases involving Judiciary itself as the party, v.i.z, Supreme Court of India Vs. Subhash Chandra Agarwal, declared that office of the Chief Justice of India is a 'public authority' under the RTI Act but simultaneously other limitations were also laid. For the first time the SC officially accepted that the CJI's office is also subject to RTI and reiterated that no constitutional authority is above scrutiny. The Subhash Agarwal case portrays the multipole nature of RTI revolution, where judiciary has a prerogative to grant the right to information but it still clutches with opacity. This Article critically analyses the reasoning and consequences of RTI on Judiciary with the help of various case judgements. While the court encapsulated the principle of transparency, the irony accompanied when the Supreme Court and High Courts continued to deny RTI applications on the grounds of 'privacy' and exemption under 'fiduciary relationships.' The court acknowledges the significance of RTI and the revolution that it has brought about in the awareness amongst the general public, yet it also becomes passive while allowing an RTI on Judiciary itself, by adding a filter layer, which will primarily presume whether the RTI Application is in 'larger public interest'. One can declare it as opacity under the 'veil of constitutional reasoning'. Two decades after the RTI Act was enacted, the guidelines issued in this case still defines the limitation on People's right to know the 'Judicial affairs' or any activity carried in the capacity of Indian Judiciary.

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ABSENCE OF PROCESS DESIGN: THE CHALLENGES IN INFORMATION RETRIEVAL

Nyayverdhan Singh⁶³

The access to public information is the key to good governance. It makes the people enjoy the lustre of being more involved and directly connected with the functioning of the Government of the nation. The Constitution of India had established the form of government that is directly responsible for its citizens. Thus, access to public information becomes the central to assure a good, transparent and accountable Government. Unfortunately, the realisation of access to information was not that easy. The RTI Act, 2005 had perfectly protected that Right to access to Information but failed to provide a model code for the establishment of administrative process design. This results in the existence of the right but absence of ease to access the public information. One can understand the importance of process design with an example. Let's assume that the Right to vote is vested in the citizens of any nation but polling stations are not established, thus there will be a right but there will be no realisation of that right. Similarly, RTI Act, 2005 profoundly vested the right to access the public information in every individual and also established the administration in the generalised terms but failed to establish the model of process design thereby there is no ease of realisation of that right. Thus, the right to access to information exists but it happens, often, that the desired information cannot be retrieved due to administrative felonies which is the result of absence of statutory established process design. In the absence of Statutory process design, access to information is solely dependent on the mercy of institution(s) and department(s). For example, sometimes the information that was desired cannot be demanded because the address of the seat of Public was not clear to the public at large.

Keywords: Access to Public Information; Accountable; Administration; Process Design; Realisation of right

REIMAGINING PRIVACY IN THE AGE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE: A SOCIO-LEGAL ANALYSIS OF INDIA'S DIGITAL PERSONAL DATA PROTECTION ACT, 2023

Ganesh Shirrang Nale⁶⁴

The rapid proliferation of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies has transformed personal data into a pivotal asset of the digital economy, generating complex challenges at the intersection of law, policy, and human rights. In this emerging data ecosystem, the protection of individual privacy and informational autonomy becomes both a legal necessity and a moral imperative. This paper offers a socio-legal analysis of India's Digital Personal Data Protection Act, 2023 (DPDPA), situating it within global developments such as the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and the OECD Principles on AI. It explores how the DPDPA seeks to balance innovation with accountability, while addressing the asymmetry between data fiduciaries and data principals. Through a critical legal analysis, the paper evaluates core

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provisions concerning consent, data processing, cross-border data transfer, and algorithmic governance. The study further examines societal dimensions—trust in technology, digital literacy, and algorithmic bias—to highlight how AI's autonomy may erode traditional notions of human oversight and dignity. By integrating legal analysis with social realities, the paper argues for a harmonized, human-centric regulatory framework that bridges law, policy, and technology. It concludes that ethical AI development in India requires not merely compliance but a transformative understanding of privacy as a collective social good and constitutional value.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Data Protection, Privacy, Digital Personal Data Protection Act 2023, Human Rights, Algorithmic Accountability

RTI AS A TOOL FOR EXPOSING POLICY DISCREPANCIES: A CASE STUDY OF EWS RESERVATION IN JAMMU AND KASHMIR

Muzamil Rashid⁶⁵

RTI (Right to Information) has emerged as a vital democratic tool that enables citizens to question authority, demand transparency, and uncover discrepancies in policy execution. By compelling public institutions to share information, RTI strengthens participatory governance and exposes the gaps between policy formulation and ground-level implementation. The present study is based on a case study in which an RTI application was filed to examine the issuance of Income and Asset Certificates under the 10 percent reservation for Economically Weaker Sections (EWS) in Jammu and Kashmir. The findings revealed that only a few certificates had been issued, with the majority of beneficiaries concentrated in urban centers, while rural applicants remained largely excluded. This reflects deep structural inequalities and shows how uniform policy criteria can disadvantage marginalized communities. The case highlights the significance of RTI not only as a transparency mechanism but also as a powerful means of evaluating the inclusiveness and effectiveness of public policies, especially in conflict-affected and socio-culturally diverse regions like Jammu and Kashmir.

Keywords: RTI Act, Transparency, Policy, Participatory governance, Economically Weaker Sections, Corruption

TRANSPARENCY AS A CONSTITUTIONAL IMPERATIVE: THE RIGHT TO KNOW IN DEMOCRATIC GOVERNANCE

Rishi Shukla⁶⁶, Priyanshu Sachan⁶⁷

Transparency is an essential attribute of constitutional democracy, transforming governance from a culture of secrecy to one of openness and accountability. In the Indian context, the concept of transparency derives its constitutional legitimacy from Article 19(1)(a) of the Constitution, which

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guarantees the freedom of speech and expression. Over the years, the Indian judiciary has expansively interpreted this provision to include the Right to Know, recognizing that freedom of expression is hollow without access to information. This paper explores transparency as a constitutional imperative and examines how the Right to Know has evolved as an integral component of democratic governance. Through a doctrinal and jurisprudential analysis, the study traces the judicial journey from State of U.P. v. Raj Narain (1975) and S.P. Gupta v. Union of India (1981) to Union of India v. Association for Democratic Reforms (2002) and People's Union for Civil Liberties v. Union of India (2004), which collectively established citizens' right to seek information as a facet of Article 19(1)(a). The paper also analyses the Right to Information Act, 2005, as a statutory manifestation of this constitutional right, institutionalizing mechanisms of transparency and participatory governance. In addition, it critically evaluates the tension between transparency and competing concerns such as privacy, national security, and administrative confidentiality issues that have gained new urgency in the digital era. The paper argues that the Right to Know is not merely a derivative of free speech but a foundational instrument for democratic legitimacy, enabling informed participation and responsible governance. Ultimately, it concludes that embedding transparency within India's constitutional and administrative ethos is vital for realizing the promise of a truly accountable and participatory democracy.

Keywords: Article 19(1)(a), Democratic Governance, Freedom of Speech and Expression, Right to Know, Transparency.

TRANSPARENCY FROM BELOW: A LEGAL–ANTHROPOLOGICAL STUDY OF THE RIGHT TO INFORMATION AND CITIZEN ACCOUNTABILITY IN JAMMU AND KASHMIR

Irfan Ali Banka⁶⁸

The Right to Information Act, 2005 marked a decisive step in strengthening democratic accountability in India. Two decades later, its meaning and impact are best understood through the experiences of those who continue to use it as a tool for justice. This paper examines the practice of the Right to Information (RTI) in Jammu and Kashmir (J&K), drawing on my work as a social and RTI activist since 2010 and as an anthropologist since 2019. It reflects on how rural and pastoral communities in J&K have used RTI to seek transparency in environmental and developmental matters—particularly in relation to water supply, river protection, and waste management. The study also draws on my participation in the National RTI Mela 2025 at Beawar, Rajasthan—the birthplace of India's RTI movement. In Beawar, the movement began in 1996 with public hearings at Chang Gate, where workers and farmers demanded access to local records under the slogan “Hamara paisa, hamara hisaab” (Our money, our account). The mela celebrated this legacy while expressing concern about recent legal and institutional setbacks, including the impact of the Digital Personal Data Protection Act, 2023, on citizens' access to information. By comparing the Beawar movement's collective origins with the current situation in J&K, the paper highlights two contrasting trajectories: one rooted in the optimism of grassroots mobilization, and the other shaped by centralization and digital constraints following the abrogation of Article 370. Using a

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legal–anthropological approach, it argues that the strength of RTI lies not only in law but in the social practice of demanding accountability. The continuing efforts of citizens in J&K demonstrate how the right to information has evolved into a form of environmental citizenship and a lived expression of democracy.

Keywords: *Right to Information, Environmental Citizenship, Jammu and Kashmir, Beawar, Democratic Accountability*

BRIDGING THE DIGITAL DIVIDE: ACCESSIBILITY CHALLENGES IN EXERCISING THE RIGHT TO INFORMATION IN INDIA

Anoushka Randeva⁶⁹

I first tried to use the Right to Information Act for something that affected thousands of students like me. The UPSC Law Optional syllabus was unclear about whether we would be tested on the old criminal laws or the newer ones. From the public library in my small hometown of Nangal, I opened the RTI portal expecting a straightforward process. Instead, the website kept freezing, payment did not go through, and my fellow students had never even seen an RTI request before. I realised that the right to information exists in theory, but for many people it is still out of reach. India now has more than 806 million internet users and almost every village has mobile network coverage. Digital services like UPI, DigiLocker and UMANG have grown rapidly. But these numbers hide the reality that access does not always mean ability. Internet usage in urban areas is still less than that in rural areas. Internet in India Report 2024 found that there were 90 million more internet users in rural areas compared to urban areas. Women too are much less likely to have their own phones or access the internet privately. There are thousands of 5G towers and fibre connections in Gram Panchayats, yet millions struggle to use digital platforms that involve technical steps, English-only interfaces or unfamiliar government procedures. This study looks at how these hidden barriers limit the use of RTI for ordinary citizens who want accountability from powerful institutions. It argues that meaningful transparency requires more than online portals. Colleges, public libraries and local governments must provide guidance and offline support. Portals should be inclusive and multilingual so that information remains a democratic right. Filing an RTI should not depend on digital privilege. It should be possible for every citizen who is willing to ask a question.

THE FUTURE OF PIO AND DISCLOSURE IN INDIA: LEGAL AND ETHICAL IMPLICATIONS IN BALANCING PRIVACY, DISCLOSURE AND AUTOMATION IN DATA GOVERNANCE

Vidhusha G V⁷⁰

The Right to Information Act (RTI) 2005, with its focus on maximum disclosure, has historically defined the role of the Public Information Officer (PIO) in Indian universities. However, the PIO is currently at a critical institutional crossroads, under pressure to comply with both the RTI Act and new data privacy regulations,

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particularly those outlined in the proposed Digital Personal Data Protection Act (DPDP). The administrative push to automate response drafting and data retrieval exacerbates this conflict. In an increasingly digitised data environment, PIOs in higher education must strike a balance between the fundamental right to privacy and the constitutional right to information. This study fills the resulting legal and ethical vacuum. As it relates to university records, this study attempts to systematically identify and map the direct legal conflicts between the requirements of the Act which demands mandatory disclosure and DPDP policies (data minimisation and consent). To assess the administrative and ethical risks associated with the use of data driven by the cyber space and the reliance to draft RTI responses, with particular emphasis on data misrepresentation, and PIO oath violations. To develop a formal, legally sound framework for PIOs that combines the three conflicting requirements of automation, disclosure, and privacy. The study will employ theoretical legal analysis of relevant laws (RTI, Digital Personal Data Protection), court decisions, and administrative circulars. It will also include a content analysis of RTI disclosures from academic institutions and a series of semi-structured interviews with current and former PIOs in selected Indian universities to document empirical issues and real-world ethical conundrums. This study expects to find the reasons that undermines the spirit of the RTI Act by making defensive, infrequent or deferred disclosures, as a result of fear of violating privacy laws. Furthermore, since discretionary disclosure decisions are inherently complex, it is hypothesised that unrestrained reliance on automated drafting tools raises the potential for inadvertent legal violations. By providing a classification of high-risk data types that require special PIO handling, this study will make a significant contribution to the Indian information justice. Develop standard operating procedures (SOPs) for the PIO office, which address the ethical use of automation technologies. Establish a path towards responsible digital data governance in the higher education sector in India by providing a single legal interpretation that guides universities in fulfilling their constitutional duty of transparency while upholding individual data rights.

Keywords: Data Governance, Legal Automation, Transparency, Digital Personal Data Protection (DPDP), Public Information Officer (PIO) and Right to Information (RTI)

RECONCILING PRIVACY RIGHTS AND PUBLIC INTEREST DEMANDS: COMPARATIVE JURISPRUDENCE AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS FOR INDIA

Alina Husain⁷¹

The paper explores how courts in India apply the necessity, proportionality, and transparency principles when dealing with clashes between privacy rights and public interest demands. An analysis has been done of national and international cases involving digital data and discovery and the court's use of proportionality standards to limit disclosure in legal proceedings where such rights are at stake. A further investigation of confidence cases where the role of public interest is generally used as an exception and the evolution of the judicial doctrine starting from the historical Spy catcher case till the cases in the recent contemporary and global legal arena has been included. Comparative analysis of the judicial approaches of various legal jurisdictions holds prominence in this regard. The paper thus, focuses on a cross-jurisdictional study of Indian case laws and the international practices from jurisdictions with

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comprehensive data protection laws such as the EU's General Data Protection Regulation and the relevant US precedents. An analysis of the DPDP Act 2023 and the recent amendments in the RTI Act, altering the landscape of privacy rights versus public interest and its alignment with international regimes and policies has been included. The paper ends with recommendations for future alignment and ways India could harmonize the legal frameworks and enforcement mechanisms, balancing the core value of protecting an individual's right and genuine public interest mandates.

ALL THAT GLITTERS IS NOT OLD”- APPLIES TO RTI ACT PASSED BY LEGISLATURE IN INDIA

Rishendra Verma⁷²

It is said “all that glitters is not gold”. Since the enforcement of the RTI Act on 12 October 2005, it has always been sounded that RTI RTI is a Powerful tool that Strengthens Democracy and Promotes good Governance by Enhancing People’s Participation; the legislative intent was to empower the citizen to promote transparency and accountability in the working of every Public Authority, reduce the gap between the information provider and the information seeker, enhance efficiency in administration of public authorities, mitigate corruption and promote good governance Stated by Shri M. Hamid Ansari, Vice President [PIB 11.7.2016]. The words about RTI Act appears rosy. But the fact remains that RTI Act is similar or disimilar to other acts in India as all acts are passed by legislature but RTI Act is a in a hybrid mode empowering citizen and the Central or State Information Commission. Obviously the former part of the act is not liked by government departments or those who fall under the ambit of RTI. It can further be seen that provision of RTI Act varies among state to state except one Central Information commission. The spirit behind the movement for Right to Information was summed up in pithy slogans like; “hamara paisa, hamara hisaab, hum janenge, hum jiyenge.” The practical experience of the author as a RTI appellate authority and as RTI applicant goes to the fact that most of cses the information is not provided in 30 days and first appeal is not decided in 45 days whereas second appeal take years to be heard. This thorny path leads to harassment and frustration to RTI applicants seeking information. The experiences gained in RTI will be discussed with suitable live exemplified to verify that what is being titled “all that glitters is not a gold” and whether the public is gainful by this RTI Act.

THE RTI-DPDP CLASH: INDIA'S SHIFTING BALANCE BETWEEN TRANSPARENCY AND PRIVACY

Bhavishya Goswami⁷³

India has always put its democratic structure on the pedestal in every issue, and now, India's democratic framework faces a dilemma cum critical juncture where recent amendments to Section 8 of the Right to Information (RTI) Act through Section 44(3) of the Digital Personal Data Protection (DPDP) Act, 2023. This article will investigate the legal and moral conflicts between the two major fundamental rights, i.e.

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right to information (derived from Article 19(1)(a) of the Indian Constitution) against the constitutionally recognised right to privacy (enshrined under Article 21). The RTI Act has been the cornerstone for promoting transparency and accountability on the part of the Indian government. It allows the citizens to access public information and has set the precedent to effectively expose corruption, improve public service delivery, and facilitate social audits of government schemes. The core issue is with regard to Section 44(3) of the DPDP Act, eliminating the “public interest override” from Section 8(1)(j) of the RTI Act, which suggests that the government is shifting towards prioritisation of individual privacy over the right to information. It has led to much criticism arguing that the original Section 8(1)(j) maintained a perfect balance between privacy and public accountability. Concerns have been raised that the government now has the liberty to classify any information as “personal” and deny providing that information. A comparative analysis of the EU’s GDPR, the UK’s Freedom of Information (FOI) Act, and FOI laws in Canada and Australia reveals that they all accommodate “public interest override” or at least a balancing test for personal data, making the DPDP different from all of them. This article, conclusively, proposes the solutions to harmonise this conflict between these two fundamental rights, which include a more precise definition of “personal information” in the DPDP Act and the establishment of a genuinely independent Data Protection Board of India. There is a significant research gap vis-à-vis this amendment, as not many academic articles and research papers are written on this significant issue. Ultimately, this article underscores that the future of India’s digital landscape hinges on what the government wants to prioritise between state control and an informed and empowered citizenry.

Keywords – Transparency, Privacy, RTI, Governance, DPDP

TRANSPARENCY IN THE AGE OF DATA PRIVACY: THE IMPACT OF THE DPDP ACT, 2023 ON INDIA’S RTI REGIME

Shreya Gautam⁷⁴, Aman Kumar⁷⁵

The Digital Personal Data Protection Act, 2023 represents a watershed moment in India’s data governance framework, redefining the boundaries between state transparency and individual privacy. This research critically examines the interface between the Right to Information Act, 2005 and the DPDP Act, 2023, focusing on their constitutional, doctrinal, and institutional interplay. While the RTI Act operationalised the citizen’s “right to know” under Article 19(1)(a), the DPDP Act embodies the “right to privacy” under Article 21 as affirmed in Justice K.S. Puttaswamy v. Union of India (2017). The amendment to Section 8(1)(j) of the RTI Act via Section 44(3) of the DPDP Act marks a paradigmatic shift: replacing a qualified exemption for “personal information” with an absolute bar on disclosure. This change, though intended to harmonise privacy with transparency, risks undermining democratic accountability by eroding the public interest override that served as the constitutional fulcrum for balancing these rights. Through comparative analysis of the EU’s GDPR and the UK’s FOIA, and examination of Indian jurisprudence (Raj Narain, Subhash Chandra Agarwal), this paper argues that the post-DPDP legal landscape privileges privacy as a state-controlled exemption rather than an individual safeguard. The study introduces the framework of “information constitutionalism,” proposing that

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transparency and privacy be treated as co-constitutive democratic rights, reconciled through proportionality and structured harm-benefit assessment. The paper concludes that India's evolving digital governance regime must avoid reducing privacy to a pretext for opacity. Reinstating the proportionality ethic within statutory interpretation, integrating oversight between the Data Protection Board and Information Commissions, and restoring the public interest test are imperative to maintain equilibrium between openness and confidentiality. Ultimately, the right to privacy and the right to information are not adversarial but interdependent, each securing the autonomy and accountability that underpin constitutional democracy.

Keywords: *Right to Information, Digital Personal Data Protection Act, Privacy, Transparency, Information Constitutionalism.*

RTI AND ACCOUNTABILITY OF PUBLIC AUTHORITIES IN REGULATING UNFAIR TRADE PRACTICES OF E-COMMERCE GIANTS IN INDIA

Swetank Kumar Singh⁷⁶

This paper analyses the evolving role of public authorities under India's Right to Information Act (RTI), focusing on the impact of key legislative and administrative changes since its introduction in 2005. The RTI Act was envisioned as a transformative tool empowering citizens to access government-held information, thereby enhancing transparency and accountability. Over time, the functions and responsibilities of public authorities have expanded and become more clearly defined through amendments, landmark judicial pronouncements, and administrative refinements. Despite these advances, significant challenges persist. The analysis identifies ongoing shortcomings such as administrative inefficiencies, inadequate training of Public Information Officers, misuse of exemption clauses, and a culture of non-disclosure that hinders effective implementation with special reference to the growing e-commerce industry. Also, it attempts to critically examine the role of the public authorities in handling and managing the cases related to e-commerce platforms and the overall whole industry and its related problems and solutions. Additionally, instances of corruption and engagement in unfair trade practices by some public officials continue to undermine the intent of the Act. By examining these persistent issues and the criticisms faced by public authorities, the paper underscores the urgent need for systemic reform. In conclusion, it offers targeted recommendations to promote better compliance, enhance institutional accountability, and revitalize the RTI framework, moving towards a more transparent and participatory governance model in India especially when it comes to the e-commerce industry.

Keywords- *public authorities, unfair trade practices, accountability, e-commerce, transparency*

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PUBLIC INTEREST VS PRIVATE LIFE: CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF THE ONGOING CONFLICT BETWEEN RIGHT TO INFORMATION AND RIGHT TO PRIVACY

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In today's digital era, the conflict between right to information and right to privacy has become a major issue. Though these rights coexist and compliment each other there still seem a conflict between the same. Right to information ensures transparency and accountability and access to public data, which is essential for democracy. On the other hand, right to privacy protect person personal data and information from being misused by the state and ensure their safeguards their freedom and dignity. With the growth of the internet, social media, and data driven technologies the boundary between what should be public and what should be private has become increasingly blur. The paper explores that how this right though complimentary to each other also tends to come into conflict and how we try to balance it in the digital era. The paper discusses the legal and ethical aspect of both the rights reviewing the key laws, policy and judgement that shape the ongoing discussion. Its also include how different countries like Indian and European union try to handle it through acts like Right to Information Act, digital personal data protection act (DPDP), and General data protection regulation (GDPR). It also covers the real-life issues related to privacy and information like online surveillance, data leaks, and information disclosure in the name of public interest. The research suggests that neither right should overpower the other instead there should strike a balance between transparency coexistence with privacy protection. This paper concludes that this balance can be achieved through strong data protection laws, digital awareness among individual, and ethical practises for both government and private organisation. In doing so the society can ensure that the right to know does not endanger the right to be left alone.

Keyword: Data, Privacy, Information, Data Protection, right to know.

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